

WORKING WITH APPEALS OF INDIVIDUALS AND LEGAL ENTITIES: PROBLEMS IN LEGISLATION AND ANALYSIS

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Annotation

This article talked about the terms of consideration of appeals of individuals and legal entities, the procedure for their extension and reduction, the timing of registration and resolution of appeals. Official statistics on the status of consideration of Appeals by state bodies and organizations are presented. The tasks envisaged in the prospects for working with the appeals put forward in the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan are covered. Comparative-legal analysis of some problematic cases associated with administrative and criminal liability for violation of legislation on appeals of individuals and legal entities. The experience of a number of foreign countries regarding the term of consideration of appeals has been studied, a comparative analysis has been carried out with our national legislation and proposals have been put forward.

Keywords: appeal, application, complaint, proposal, list, resolution, assignment, term, people's reception, strategy, platform, legislative acts.

It is well known that consistent efforts are being made in our country to improve communication between government agencies and the population, ensure the reliable protection of citizens' rights and freedoms, and introduce modern mechanisms for solving their problems.

In particular, nearly ten normative legal documents related to this area have been adopted in recent years, including the newly revised Law "On Appeals of Individuals and Legal Entities."

Moreover, the establishment of the Virtual and People's Reception Offices of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the creation of "Hotlines" in government bodies and organizations, not only helps ease the burdens of citizens but also serves to prevent various inconveniences.

In addition, the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026, approved by Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60 dated January 28, 2022 (hereinafter referred to as the Development Strategy), outlines seven strategic directions and 100 goals. Among them, Strategic

Direction 1, Goal 11, is dedicated to improving the system for handling appeals from individuals and legal entities. This includes creating a centralized system to collect all appeals submitted to government bodies, establishing digital oversight over the timing and quality of their consideration, and ensuring the prompt and high-quality review of appeals related to issues that directly affect the daily lives of the population—identified as a key priority.

Furthermore, Paragraph 39 of the State Program for the implementation of the Development Strategy in the “Year of Honoring Human Dignity and Active Neighborhood” specifies the requirement to ensure that, by the end of 2022, all appeals submitted to government bodies and organizations are processed through a Unified Online Platform for Working with Appeals.

According to statistical data, in the first half of 2022, nearly **773,000** appeals were received by government bodies and organizations, as well as by local state authorities. While the total number of appeals decreased by **66,000**, or **8%**, compared to the previous year, there was a sharp increase in the number of appeals related to:

- provision of material assistance to those in need (by **17,000**, or **3.7 times**),
- enforcement of court decisions in civil cases (**2,200**, or **2.2 times**),
- providing food assistance to those in need (**1,700**, or **2.3 times**),
- installation of natural gas meters (**1,200**, or **3.5 times**),
- and the conduct of cadastral employees (**981** appeals, or **3.9 times**).

The above-mentioned statistical data and the tasks assigned to government agencies demonstrate the urgency of the issue of handling appeals and the necessity of continuously improving the relevant legislation.

Various legal theorists have provided different definitions of the concept of the right to appeal.

For instance, according to A.A. Drakov and A.P. Lyubimova, the right to appeal is the right of a citizen (a foreign citizen or a stateless person) to address competent authorities with proposals, applications, requests, or complaints in oral or written form to resolve relevant issues [3]. However, this definition does not fully disclose the purpose and characteristics of the right to appeal. Moreover, it does not mention electronic appeals as a form of appeal.

Notably, in this definition, a request is presented as a separate type of appeal. Meanwhile, according to the legislation of several countries, including the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Appeals of Individuals and Legal Entities,” a request is not recognized as a separate type of appeal.

As noted by Y. Khrumalova and M. Mikhaylovskiy, appeals serve as an important source of information for the state to promptly and effectively respond to the needs and demands of society. They are also an effective means of communication with the population to fulfill individual freedoms and interests [4].

According to Article 28 of Law No. O'RQ-445 of the Republic of Uzbekistan, adopted on September 11, 2017, "On Appeals of Individuals and Legal Entities," an application or complaint must be reviewed within fifteen days from the date of receipt by the relevant government body, organization, or official authorized to resolve the issue on its merits. If additional investigation and/or verification or the collection of supplementary documents is required, the period for consideration may be extended to up to one month [5].

That is, parts one and two of the article stipulate the period within which applications or complaints must be considered and the conditions under which this period may be extended. However, part three of the same article provides that a proposal must be reviewed within up to one month from the date it is received by the relevant government body, organization, or official—excluding proposals that require additional investigation.

From the content of the article, it can be concluded that the timeframe for considering applications and complaints, as well as the issue of extending that timeframe, is clearly defined. However, there is no provision specifying how long proposals requiring additional study should be reviewed. This ambiguity may lead to differing interpretations of the legal norm and inconsistent practices in its application.

When discussing the timeframe for reviewing appeals, it is also important to refer to international practices.

For example, under the legislation of the U.S. state of Texas, appeals from citizens must be reviewed within **10 business days** [6].

According to the official website of the UK government, appeals are to be considered within **20 business days**. If additional investigations are required, this period may be extended up to **12 weeks** [7].

Additionally, the UK Ombudsman reviews complaints within a period of up to **8 weeks** [8].

According to Article 12 of the Federal Law of the Russian Federation dated May 2, 2006, No. 59-FZ "On the Procedure for Considering Appeals," appeals must be reviewed within **30 calendar days**. If there are valid grounds, this

period may be extended for an additional **30 days** by the head of the organization [9].

As can be seen from the above international practices, there are several differences compared to our national legislation. For example, in Texas, the timeframe is calculated in **business days**; in the UK, the **extended review period is significantly longer**; and in the Russian Federation, there is **no explicitly defined 15-day period** for appeals that do not require further investigation.

Moreover, according to Paragraph 41 of the Model Regulation approved by the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 341 dated May 7, 2018, "On Approval of the Model Regulation on the Procedure for Handling Appeals from Individuals and Legal Entities in Government Bodies, State Institutions, and Organizations with State Participation" [10], in certain cases, the head or deputy head of a government body or organization has the right to reduce the appeal review period.

However, this regulation and other relevant legislative acts do not specify **how and to what exact extent** the head of an organization may shorten the timeframe for reviewing appeals.

This ambiguity could lead to **varied interpretations** of the legal norm and cause **practical difficulties** for the employees handling appeals.

For instance, if a head of an organization repeatedly instructs an employee to review multiple appeals within **three days**, naturally, the employee may not be able to fulfill their other official duties on time or to thoroughly analyze every claim raised in the appeal.

Such situations may result in **poor-quality review** of appeals and an **increase in repeat submissions**. Therefore, we believe it would be appropriate for the **procedure and maximum limits** for reducing the appeal review period to be clearly and strictly defined in legislative documents.

In conclusion, it is worth emphasizing that the activities related to the appeals of individuals and legal entities serve as a specific indicator reflecting the extent to which a particular state addresses the problems of its population, how effectively government bodies and organizations are fulfilling their assigned functions, and how successful the ongoing reforms in the country are proving to be. Therefore, the legislation governing this area must be subject to continuous analytical review and improvement based on best international practices.

References:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-60 dated January 28, 2022, "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026" // URL: <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/-5841063>
2. Resolution of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. SQ-622-IV dated September 13, 2022, "On the State of Work with Appeals in the System of State Bodies and Organizations in the First Half of 2022" // URL: <https://lex.uz/docs/6198724>
3. Lyubimova A.P. Civil Lobbyism: Procedures and Technologies of Citizens' Appeals. – Moscow, 1998;
4. Dvorak A.A. Implementation of Citizens' Constitutional Right to Appeal in the Russian Federation: Dissertation for the Candidate of Legal Sciences. – Moscow, 2004
5. Khrumalova Yu.V. The Right of Citizens to Appeal to Public Authorities as a Form of Feedback Between the Population and the State Apparatus. // Civil Society in the Era of Global Informatization: Proceedings of the III International Youth Scientific Conference. – Moscow, 2011. – P. 284
6. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. O'RQ-445 dated September 11, 2017, "On Appeals of Individuals and Legal Entities" // URL: <https://lex.uz/docs/-3336169>
7. Complaints Overview // URL: <https://www.texasattorneygeneral.gov/opengovernment/governmental-bodies/complaints-overview>
8. Complaints and Appeals: Detailed Information // URL: <https://www.gov.uk/topic/dealing-with-hmrc/complaints-appeals>
9. Complaining to an Ombudsman // URL: <https://www.citizensadvice.org.uk/consumer/get-more-help/how-to-use-an-ombudsman-in-england/>
10. On the Procedure for Consideration of Appeals by Citizens of the Russian Federation // URL: https://www.wto.org/english/thewto_e/acc_e/rus_e/wtaccrus48a8_leg_3.pdf
11. Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 341 dated May 7, 2018, "On the Approval of the Model Regulation on the Procedure for Handling Appeals of Individuals and Legal Entities in State Bodies, State Institutions, and Organizations with State Participation" // URL: <https://lex.uz/docs/-3730228>